

THE NEED FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS AND PARENTS PARTNERSHIP IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *It has been observed that most early childhood education providers in Nigeria seem not to understand the roles of parents and guardian in providing quality education for early childhood pupils. Quality early childhood programs can change the trajectory of a child's health and well-being. Early years education lays a solid foundation for a child's lifelong learning journey. It shapes their cognitive, social, and emotional development in so many ways. This will be possible when there is synergy between the school, teacher and the parents/guardian. Partnership involves parents, families and practitioners working together to benefit children. Each recognizes, respects and values what the other does and says. Partnership involves responsibility on both sides. This paper looked at the two important building blocks of positive partnerships between the school, teacher and the parents; family centered and communication. The paper also discussed the need for partnership in early childhood education in Nigeria and how to promote partnership among school management early childhood educators and parents. The paper recommends that all early childhood education schools in Nigeria should constitute a formidable parent-teachers forum, while the Nigerian Association of Early Childhood Education providers should collaborate with relevant authorities to organize seminars and workshops for parents/guardian on their roles and responsibilities to support their child's education and collaborate with all institutions offering Early Childhood to organize Seminars/workshop for early child educators on how to partner with parents*

Introduction

The years between birth and entering primary school are a period of intense learning and development for children, where the foundations

are laid for future social, emotional and intellectual development. Creating positive learning environments for babies, toddlers and preschoolers is one of the key elements of giving

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every child the opportunity to reach his or her full potential throughout life. For this reason, developing strong, positive and effective partnerships in early childhood education is vital to the achievement of children's successful learning and development (Department of Education and Early Childhood Development, Victoria State Government, 2024).

Evidence of the importance of the early years to long term learning, behaviour, employment, and health status has been growing for decades. Research has revealed that serious risks to infant and toddler development must be avoided or reduced to promote healthy development and put protective factors in place. The importance of nurturing care and the roles of families, quality childcare, supportive communities, and enabling policy environments has been well documented (Black et al., 2017). Research regarding accessible and affordable quality childcare is bringing renewed attention to this neglected area (UNICEF, 2019c). Increasing evidence reveals the effectiveness of encouraging nurturing care and early childhood interventions. Supportive environments, captured by the term 'nurturing care,' can promote optimal infant development (World Health Organization, UNICEF, World Bank Group 2018; Britto et al., 2017; Hanson & Gluckman, 2016).

Partnerships in early childhood education frequently involve the integration of all stakeholders in early childhood education including the private and government providers. Sometimes, a partnership means trying to understand things from another person's point of view. Every now and then, this can be difficult. However, partnerships can take many forms, and

the nature and extent of each partnership will vary according to the needs of the child, the school and the early childhood service providers (Kids Matter, Australia Mental Health Initiative, 2023).

This is supported by UNESCO Global Partnership Strategy (GPS) for Early Childhood that was formed in December 2021. The GPS is a bridging strategy which responds to a lack of services ranging from pre-primary education, health, nutrition, sanitation, and child protection worldwide. It supports States in their obligations to ensure quality Early Childhood to children and families and aligns with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development's Target 4.2, which aims to ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality pre-primary care and education to enable them to be ready for primary school. The overall goal of the GPS is to ensure that early childhood development, and investment services are fully inclusive, accessible, affordable, gender-responsive and equitable for each child. Effective policies and services for early childhood education should allow for maximum return on investment into child and family development, to transform society and build better communities (UNESCO, 2022).

Despite this laudable programme by the UNESCO, there is little or no partnership programme in place among early childhood educators in Nigeria in nearly all aspects of early childhood education ranging from lack of unified curriculum, lack of facilities and equipment, standardization of certification of professional and other issues. To achieve the goals of Global Partnership strategy for early childhood education, there is need for partnership among

the stakeholders, which was the focus of this paper.

Within early childhood education, families and staff may be in different stages of building partnerships. Some families and staff may have a relationship, but not yet developed a partnership. Some may be in the process of building a partnership. Others will have built and maintained partnerships over a long period of time and know each other quite well. Families may choose to be involved with their early childhood service at different levels. Whether a family and service shares a relationship or a partnership, they are able to work together to support children. Building partnerships takes time and ongoing effort and everyone needs to keep working at it; taking small steps works best. Families and staff who build partnerships experience more satisfaction when they interact with one another. Children benefit from this positive environment as it helps promote their mental health and wellbeing (Baker & Manfredi, 2004).

One of the most rewarding experiences is to expose the child to the joys and benefits of early childhood education. It's an invaluable time when children quickly learn that they are part of a community, that they need to share with and care about others, and that there are social norms to follow for the benefit of all. These elements are only heightened when parents, teachers, school management and other stakeholders work closely in tandem to foster a child's potential early on. For young children, this is a time of great exploration and when they start to develop a sense of self. When children are surrounded by people who care deeply for them

both at home and in the classroom, it only serves to help them to thrive in every setting (Harbor Child Care, 2024).

Open and clear communication is vital in keeping parents informed about their child's progress, milestones, and areas in need of improvement (Britto, Lye, Proulx, Yousafzai, Matthews, Vaivada, Perez-Escamilla, Rao, Ip, Fernald, MacMillan & Bhutta, 2017). The more open the communication can be between parents and teachers, the more a child will benefit. Young children grow at a fast pace and some develop faster than others. When parents and teachers have open communication, they can foster productive dialogue to keep each other informed. There should be a clear system established in advance so if there is something urgent that needs to be told, neither a teacher nor parent will miss important updates (Harbor Child Care, 2024).

Parents-teachers conferences are also a crucial aspect of early childhood learning. It's important that parents come prepared with questions about their child, but also come with an open mind when listening to what a teacher may have to say. It's always helpful when parents take a moment to show appreciation to the teacher who spends so much time with their child on a daily basis. When parents and teachers get to know each other, they can better decide when there is something going on with a child that needs to be discussed and can't wait until a formal time to meet is scheduled (Harbor Child Care, 2024).

However, varying schedules and limited time can make it challenging to connect with every family regularly. Young children flourish when the

adults caring for them work well together. Families and staff can share discussions about how children are going and how best to meet their needs. Families know their child's strengths, personality, moods and behaviours very well. Staff can also get to know a child well through their daily experiences and can share their understanding of how children develop. When families and staff work together they can exchange information and focus on meeting each child's needs and supporting their development (Open University, 2025).

According to UNICEF (2019c), partnerships allow children to see important people in their lives working well together. When children see positive communication between their parents or guardian and staff, they begin to learn it is important to build healthy relationships. For example, children who see their parents or guardian communicating well and being friendly with staff can learn this is how to relate well to others. Children can trust and feel safe with staff who are respected and supported by their family and who respect and support their family in return. Children can then feel comfortable at their early childhood service and enjoy positive experiences. Children feel valued and important when families and staff support and respect each other equally and take an interest in their lives. Parents and guardian who are positively involved with their children can help reduce mental health difficulties.

In a partnership, families and staff can share their experiences with each other and their understanding of how their bond is important to a child. Children are still developing and find it hard to separate their experiences from one

environment to another, for example, being comfortable in the care of those at home as well as staff. When families and staff are in a partnership, children are more able to negotiate differences between settings, such as home and the early childhood service, as they see the adults who care for them working together. For example, children are able to manage different rules and routines in different places when they have an understanding of what the rules and routines are and when they are supported. The greater the predictability in care, the easier it is for children to develop a sense of who they are and what they can expect from those around them (Baker & Manfredi, 2004).

When staff shares positive bonds with children's families, it helps the staff feel more connected, valued, rewarded and appreciated. Staff can easily respond to children's needs by understanding a child's relationship with their parents, guardian and siblings. Staff can also develop a deeper understanding of how each family would like their child to be raised. Having a 'bigger picture' of a child's world allows staff to relate to children in a way that makes them feel understood which then strengthens relationships. Relationships and partnerships assist staff feel confident and satisfied in their role of supporting the child and their development (UNICEF, 2019d).

According to Stonehouse (2001), the characteristics of effective partnerships include; mutual respect, trust, sensitivity to the perspective of the other, or empathy, on-going open 'both ways' communication, a common goal that is clear and agreed on, namely the child's well-being, teamwork, the absence of

rivalry or competition, recognition and valuing of the unique contribution and strengths of the partner and shared decision making. For any positive relationship among the staff and parents to be workable, there is need for building blocks for the partnership. Building and maintaining partnerships takes time and efforts from the people involved. There are two important building blocks of positive partnerships between families and staff. These are family-centred care and communication (Kids Matter, Australia Mental Health Initiative, 2023).

Family-centred care: Family-centred care is about families and staff being actively involved in the care and education of children. Utilising family knowledge and understanding, resources, and strengths assists shared decision making for children in the early childhood service. Family centred care also occurs when staff shares information about children in an open, respectful and collaborative way. This enables parents and guardians to feel acknowledged in their parenting role and have their own needs acknowledged. This helps provide the base for partnerships between families and staff (Save the Children, 2002).

Communication: Effective communication helps build partnerships. Honest, respectful communication and a genuine interest in one another helps to build trust. Trust allows people to be open about their thoughts and feelings. For families, effective communication assists them in explaining how they would like their child cared for in the service. For example, when a family member describes how they manage a behaviour at home so a similar approach can be used in the service. Supporting learners is a collaborative

process that involves effective partnership working. The role and views of the parents, guardian, and child or young person are very important (Save the Children, 2002).

Parents, guardian or someone else involved with the family (e.g. social worker, health visitor) may have brought concerns to the teacher's notice in the first instance. The involvement of professionals will vary depending on the needs of the learner. It is important that partners, parents and learners are provided with information about the entitlements and support that are available. Information is freely available through your local authority and a range of third sector organisations. It is helpful to communicate the current support given to a child or young person as parents may otherwise be unaware of the range of adaptations that are routinely offered (Achanfuo, 2010).

Effective communication and collaboration between parents and educators play a pivotal role in ensuring a child's success in preschool. A strong partnership can significantly impact a child's development and learning experience. Additionally, it delves into practical strategies for parents and teachers to enhance these partnerships, ensuring that a child's preschool experience is enriched with holistic support and tailored guidance. Together, parents and educators play a pivotal role in shaping the educational journey of young learners, setting a strong foundation for their future growth and development (Britto, Lye, Proulx, Yousafzai, Matthews, Vaivada, Perez-Escamilla, Rao, Fernald, MacMillan & Bhutta, 2017).

Communicating well involves two-way sharing of information, helps develop a common

understanding and means it is easier for parents, guardian and staff to support one another. The following information may be beneficial for communication:

- Beliefs and values in families and services
- The child's interests, strengths and challenging behaviours
- Social supports outside of the early childhood service
- Early childhood milestones and expected behaviours
- Family expectations and circumstances (UNESCO, 2022).

Working in partnership involves listening to, acknowledging and valuing the contributions that stakeholders make with regard to the growth and overall development of the child. It will be necessary to build and strengthen family and community participation in Early Childhood education programmes and empower families to participate in supporting their programmes and raising awareness at local, regional and central levels. Early childcare, so beneficial for mothers working outside the home, has been neglected and urgently needs expanded investment preferably from education ministries that can provide normative guidance, quality improvement, and training for caregivers (Devercelli & Beaton-Day, 2020; UNICEF, 2019d). Parents/carers are often looking for ways to be more actively involved with school to support their child's education. It is known that when schools engage well with parents/carers, outcomes for learners both at school and at home are improved. Regular sharing of information can help support early identification of concerns and lead to the implementation of early

intervention. Not all parents/guardian feel comfortable in this partnership role for a variety of reasons. For example:

- parents/guardian may have low levels of literacy and/or not be used to having their views respected.
- parents/ guardian may have had previous negative experiences of engaging with schools and be reluctant to be involved.
- parents/ guardian may have difficulty prioritising time to attend meetings perhaps due to other caring responsibilities.
- sharing information about the learner's abilities and needs, and how these impact on home life and education.
- setting and prioritising shared meaningful learning and wellbeing targets and goals.
- sharing and advising on the suitability of specific strategies to use, both in school and at home, which support the environment (physical and social), structures and routines, motivation and skills.

The need for partnership in early childhood education in Nigeria

To support the development, improvement and monitoring of child development, early learning, and quality service standards:

Child learning outcomes mainly result from interplay between the quality of learning environments, adult-child and child-child interactions in home environments, and teaching facilitated by teachers in Early Childhood Education settings in collaboration with parents. Early Childhood Education from birth to five years should have a clear set of child development and learning outcomes that they work towards achieving in line with a broad child

development, pedagogical and curriculum framework. Child parents/guardian and teachers should gain skills to work effectively with children from diverse backgrounds, needs and abilities in an inclusive manner. They should support and assess their progress in achieving expected outcomes and use assessment results to improve practice (World Health Organization, UNICEF, World Bank Group, 2018).

To improve the quantity and quality of the early childhood workforce: Considerable evidence exists that the early childhood workforce (e.g. teachers, educators, home visitors, childcare workers, health care workers) is the key driver of nurturing care and quality education. When qualified, well trained and supported, and enjoying decent working conditions, they provide inclusive care and quality learning experiences that lead to positive child development outcomes. To attain effective early childcare, learning through play, health services, and social protection systems, increased attention must be given to building a strong early childhood workforce and implementing measures to encourage professionalisation and the pursuit of pathways to accreditation or certification (Britto, Yoshikawa & Boller, 2011).

Issues include developing improved culturally appropriate curricula, accreditation of Early Childhood Education programmes, enhancing qualification and certification frameworks; early recruitment and deployment, including supporting quality health, protection and education workers in rural, remote and disadvantaged areas; early childhood education, inclusive and continuous professional

development, and effective appraisal systems for teachers and caregivers; practice-based supervision, mentoring and pedagogical support; and the development of career development pathways, salary scales and improved working conditions (G-20. 2018).

To promote at least one year of free and compulsory quality pre-primary education in sector planning, budgeting and implementation: In line with SDG Target 4.2 and to ensure wider access to Early Childhood Education and pre-primary education for all children, governments need to plan for and implement quality Early Childhood Education programmes as part of their national and sub-national education sector plans. Early Childhood Education programmes of the education sectors in many nations, including initial education, childcare and development, parenting support and pre-primary education, should be linked with health, nutrition, water and sanitation, and child rights and protection. Multi-sectoral initiatives of education ministries should be strategically designed and sufficiently funded, staffed, supervised and monitored (Britto, Lye, Proulx, Yousafzai, Matthews, Vaivada, Perez-Escamilla, Rao, Fernald, MacMillan & Bhutta, 2017).

To strengthening the Educational Foundation: Parent-teacher partnerships play a crucial role in strengthening the educational foundation of students. When parents and teachers collaborate effectively, they create a cohesive support system that enhances a student's learning experience in various ways.

- **Consistency in Learning:** Parents and teachers can work together to ensure that

students receive consistent messages and expectations both at home and in the classroom. This consistency helps students understand and follow rules and routines more effectively, leading to better learning outcomes.

- **Tailored Support:** Parents have unique insights into their child's strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles. When teachers collaborate with parents, they can use this information to customize their teaching methods and materials, providing a more personalized education that addresses the specific needs and preferences of each student.
- **Continuous Monitoring:** Parent-teacher partnerships enable ongoing monitoring of a student's progress. Teachers can share regular updates on academic performance and behaviour with parents, allowing them to intervene early if a student is struggling or falling behind. This proactive approach prevents issues from escalating and ensures timely support.

To foster a supportive Learning Environment: A supportive learning environment is essential for a student's overall well-being and academic success. Parent-teacher partnerships contribute significantly to creating and maintaining such an environment.

- **Emotional Support:** Students excel when they feel safe, valued, and supported. Teachers can work with parents to identify any emotional or social challenges their child may be facing, such as bullying or peer conflicts. Together, they can implement

strategies to address these issues and promote a positive school environment.

- **Open Communication:** Effective communication between parents and teachers fosters a sense of trust and collaboration. Parents should feel comfortable discussing concerns or sharing insights about their child's emotional well-being with teachers. In turn, teachers can provide guidance on how parents can support their child's emotional development at home.
- **Conflict Resolution:** Conflicts may arise in any learning environment. When they do, a strong parent-teacher partnership can facilitate a quick and constructive resolution. By addressing conflicts together, parents and teachers demonstrate conflict-resolution skills that students can learn from and apply in their own lives (UNESCO, 2022).

To address Academic and Behavioural Challenges: Academic and behavioural challenges are a part of every student's educational journey. Parent-teacher partnerships are instrumental in identifying and addressing these challenges effectively.

- **Early Intervention:** Early detection and intervention are critical when students face academic or behavioural difficulties. Teachers can share their observations with parents, such as changes in study habits or classroom behaviour, to collectively identify potential issues and strategies for improvement.
- **Individualized Plans:** In cases where a student requires additional support, parents and teachers can collaborate on creating individualized education plans (IEPs) or

behaviour intervention plans (BIPs). These plans outline specific goals, strategies, and resources to help the student overcome challenges.

- **Consistent Expectations:** Parents and teachers can work together to establish consistent expectations and consequences for academic performance and behaviour. When students know that both home and school environments share these expectations, they are more likely to meet them.
- **Resource Sharing:** Teachers can inform parents about available resources, such as tutoring, counselling services, or extracurricular activities, that can support a student's academic and behavioural development. Parents can also share their insights and experiences with such resources, contributing to a broader understanding of what works best for the student (DiYES International School, 2023).

How to promote partnership among school management early childhood educators and parents in Nigeria

Regular Parent-Teacher Meetings and Updates:

Regular parent-teacher meetings and updates are a cornerstone of effective communication between educators and parents.

Establish a Connection: Parent-teacher meetings offer an opportunity for parents and teachers to build a strong rapport. Face-to-face interactions create a personal connection that can foster trust and collaboration. Parents feel more comfortable discussing their child's progress and challenges when they have a personal relationship with the teacher (Osher & Osher, 2002).

Holistic Understanding: During meetings, teachers can provide comprehensive insights into a student's academic performance, behaviour, and social interactions. Parents gain a more holistic understanding of their child's school life, allowing them to provide more targeted support at home.

Set Goals: Parent-teacher meetings are an ideal forum to set academic and behavioural goals for the student. By establishing clear objectives collaboratively, both parents and teachers can work together to support the student's progress and development.

Tracking Progress: Regular meetings help track a student's progress over time. Parents can see the evolution of their child's learning journey and celebrate achievements. Additionally, if a student is facing challenges, teachers and parents can collaborate on strategies for improvement.

Engage in School Activities and Events:

Engaging in school activities and events is a valuable way for parents to actively participate in their child's preschool journey (DiYES International School, 2023).

Conclusion

The significance of parent-teacher partnerships is undeniable when it comes to strengthening the educational foundation of early childhood pupils, fostering a supportive learning environment, and addressing academic and behavioural challenges. These partnerships create a collaborative and holistic approach to education, ensuring that pupils receive the guidance and support they need to excel academically, emotionally, and socially.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. All early childhood education schools in Nigeria should constitute a formidable parent-teachers forum
2. The Federal and State Ministries of Education should come up with a template that will give parents/guardian the opportunities to be part of the early childhood schools decision making.
3. Nigerian Association of Early Childhood Education providers should collaborate with relevant authorizes to organize seminars and workshops for parents/guardian on their roles and responsibilities to support their child' s education
4. Nigeria Association for Early Childhood Education should collaborate with all institutions offering Early Childhood to organize Seminars/workshop for early child educators on how to partner with parents

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